

PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS ON SAP DATABASE (HANA) BY USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) AND AUTOMATED MACHINE LEARNING CAPABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

The essential necessity of the hour is for predictive analytics! Human lives have been affected, either deliberately or unknowingly, by it. One does not often recognize how deeply artificial intelligence has penetrated society and the effects it has had on it. In accordance with the preferences and browsing patterns, the shopping list is indexed. Because of the length of time that a person spends looking at a picture or a video, they are compelled to examine adverts. The watering schedule is adjusted accordingly when the sprinkler is able to detect the temperature. Just a few short months from now, there will be smart kitchens available in every single home. Many companies have decided to permanently automate their procedures in order to stay ahead of the competition in an augmented analytics-based industry. These groups have benefited from this decision's outcomes. Finding and implementing cutting-edge AI and ML technology is a top enterprise priority. Because of this rush, the market has become more open to creative expression, and a new period of rivalry has begun in the direction of developing and bringing the greatest items in their respective categories. Additionally, it encourages an atmosphere of innovative construction inside the sector, in addition to undergoing continuous renovations within itself. The reliability of the information conveyed by this technology will determine how well it performs. That being said, companies must have a firm grasp on the what, why, and how of deploying AI and ML technologies if they want to succeed in this area.

Keywords: Business Intelligence, SAP Cloud, Predictive analytics, SAP Analytics Cloud, Data intelligence.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Among the most prominent technological trends that will emerge in 2023 are Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning. Within the context of Intelligent Data Applications, this blog post delves further into the manner in which SAP HANA Cloud makes use of these functionalities to enable advanced analysis. It would like to bring to your attention that this blog post has a seven-minute interview with christoph.morgen, who is an expert on SAP HANA Cloud Machine Learning. In this conversation, he discusses SAP HANA Cloud, machine learning, and artificial intelligence in a thoughtful way.

Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning

Artificial intelligence (AI) apart from ML, the field of machine learning: When we talk about the first one, we are referring to the ability of a computer to carry out tasks that have historically been dependent on human intelligence. The field of artificial intelligence includes a subfield known as machine learning. The extended training of machine learning models on a large number of example data points allows them to develop insight. Machine learning algorithms seek out patterns so they may make predictions and suggestions based on such patterns. Furthermore, these algorithms show promise for efficiency improvements when exposed to fresh data and experiences, and they are quite adaptable [1-2].

Databases with Built-In Machine Learning: A Game-Changer for Powerful Insights

The value of data is contingent upon the ability to derive the appropriate insights from the study of the data. As a result, the capabilities of machine learning that are incorporated into a database are an important benefit in a variety of different areas.

As is the case with the embedded machine learning that SAP HANA Cloud provides, the movement of data is greatly reduced because the data already exists within the database. By leveraging local data, models may be trained on massive data sets, guaranteeing that the system can scale [3].

It also decreases complexity, which is a benefit because external machine learning engines typically require installation, configuration, and management:

Concerns concerning safety are frequently raised whenever the topic of machine learning is discussed. Access is directly regulated by the database security measures when a built-in engine is utilized through the use of engine.[4]: Security and governance are inextricably linked to the capabilities of machine learning that are an integral part of the system. User management can be accomplished through the use of straightforward SQL queries, in the same manner that database access can be granted. To add insult to injury, the governance of the model is simplified when compared to the use of external machine learning. To assess the suggested model's efficacy, one can employ SQL statements or multi-model engines, like a graph engine.

Also, the utilization of a standardized user interface is a driving force behind adoption across all levels of users. It is possible to solve fundamental jobs with SQL, which opens up the world of machine learning without the need to become an expert in R or Python. While certain challenges continue to require data scientists, basic activities can be done with SQL. This is a very significant advantage, especially when one considers the fact that qualified data scientists are hard to come by and expensive:

Common Machine Learning Use Cases

Classification, regression, and time series forecasting are the three most common use cases in machine learning. Figure 1 shows an algorithm's classification capability, which allows it to predict a class for a given data point (example).

This could include, for instance, determining whether or not an email being sent is considered spam, or determining whether or not recent client behavior should be considered churn. While these two examples indeed illustrate binary classifications, the reality is that classification problems are much more complex than that. For tasks like checking if a handwritten character is known or not, they can also be multi-class, as seen in figure 2. When more than one label can be predicted for a given sample, like in picture classification, multi-labels are employed.

Here, the machine learning system makes a prediction about the presence of particular things, such as a home, a dog, and a tree. In addition, these can be imbalanced, which means that the amount of instances included in each class is not spread in an equal manner. Examples that are considered to be classics are medical diagnostic tests and fraud detection[5].

Fig 1: Binary Classification

Fig 2: Multi-Class Classification

The ability of an algorithm to predict a continuous target variable instead of a discrete one is fully captured by the term "regression."

As an illustration, estimating a person's income by taking into account aspects such as their level of education, years of experience in the workforce, seniority, and location.[6]

It is for this reason that regression is used to establish a link between variables by estimating the degree to which one variable influences another. Linear regression, which involves finding the line that best fits the given data, is the most common variety since it is easy to use for forecasting and prediction.[6]

Forecasting based on time series comprise the final scenario. These algorithms provide predictions about future data points by utilizing data from a time series that has been collected in the past. This scenario presents its own unique issues, many of which are closely related to the time component. These challenges include seasonality, shifting patterns, the effects of holidays, and the scarcity of data. The need for demand forecasting and space planning in retail establishments is a prime example of this. Time series forecasting can be used in this context to anticipate inventory levels during strong demand periods and minimize overstocking during periods of reduced demand [7-9].

2. MACHINE LEARNING IN SAP HANA CLOUD

Specifically, SAP HANA Cloud provides two libraries that contain a wide variety of methods in the field of machine learning [10-13]. Predictive Analysis Library (PAL) is designed to accommodate all traditional machine learning situations, including classification, regression, and time series forecasting, which are utilized by professionals. A more straightforward syntax that is appropriate for non-specialists is provided by the Automated Predictive Library. Either SQL or SQLScript can be used to access either of the libraries [14-16].

For the purpose of maximizing synergies, the SAP HANA Cloud Machine Learning client makes it possible for the data scientist to continue working in the environment of their choice (Python, R, etc.), while also facilitating the sharing of code in a manner that is easy.[17-21] The data scientist can use their skills to construct the machine learning scenario, and then bring the

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objects to the application developer for further processing. After that, the developer can integrate intelligence into data applications by using a SQL query to retrieve the machine learning object within the actual application code.

For example, one use case of machine learning in SAP HANA Cloud is the capacity to predict employee attrition [22-24]. This machine learning tutorial by christoph.morgen shows you how to build a model that can predict which workers will quit your company. During the demonstration, our SAP HANA expert makes use of a classification technique. Afterwards, the model is trained and its output is assessed using a test data set. [25-29] The model concludes with a prediction of staff turnover.

In light of this, the Machine Learning capabilities of SAP HANA Cloud make it possible for users to formulate a prediction without the requirement of having specialist knowledge in data science.

Example of an Intelligent Data Application using Machine Learning

An enormous manufacturing facility is overseen by a business that uses sensors to send data on the equipment's health into a SAP HANA Cloud database. The consumer is cognizant of the fact that unscheduled maintenance on their production machinery causes monetary losses and impacts their degree of contentment. The implementation of an Intelligent Data Application is necessary. By uploading sensor data into SAP HANA Cloud, the built-in machine learning algorithms can forecast when the system would likely go down by combining historical data with current values.

Now that the organization is able to anticipate problems and take preventative measures, it will no longer have to go through the awful "fire drill." Not only does this understanding of potential downtime lead to an increase in production productivity, but it also ensures that "everyone" is content.

3. LEVERAGING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN SAP S/4HANA

One technology that has recently arisen as a game-changer in many different sectors is the so-called "artificial intelligence" (AI). With this innovation, businesses can streamline their operations, make data-driven decisions, and tap into new opportunities. Businesses can take advantage of intelligent automation, predictive analytics, and intelligent insights with the help of SAP S/4HANA, the leading intelligent enterprise resource planning (ERP) solution, which seamlessly integrates AI capabilities.

In this article, the confluence of artificial intelligence and SAP S/4HANA is investigated, with a focus on the advantages and applications of AI in the process of driving intelligent enterprise transformation.

Here are some of the benefits:

AI-Powered Automation:

- Intelligent Robotic Process Automation (RPA): Using SAP S/4HANA, repetitive and rule-based tasks may be automated by bots powered by artificial intelligence, which reduces the amount of manual labor required, improves accuracy, and speeds up the execution of processes.
- Smart Document Processing: Intelligent extraction of information from documents is made possible by artificial intelligence technologies such as optical character recognition (OCR), which also improves data capture and automates a variety of tasks, including invoice processing, contract administration, and more.

Predictive Analytics and Forecasting:

- Machine Learning for Demand Forecasting: The machine learning algorithms that are built in SAP S/4HANA enable accurate demand forecasting, optimization of inventory levels, and improvement of supply chain planning. These capabilities are achieved through the analysis of historical data and different external factors.
- Predictive Maintenance: The use of artificial intelligence algorithms allows for the analysis of sensor data and patterns of equipment performance to forecast the need for maintenance, hence minimizing downtime, maximizing asset utilization, and enhancing operational efficiency.

Intelligent Insights and Decision Support:

- AI-Enabled Analytics: Using AI techniques like machine learning and natural language processing (NLP), SAP S/4HANA provides users with sophisticated analytics and contextual insights. This enables users to make decisions based on accurate information.
- Real-time Insights: Through the use of AI, data streams are continuously analyzed, allowing for proactive decision-making, early anomaly detection, and real-time monitoring of critical performance indicators.

Enhanced User Experience:

- Conversational AI and Chatbots: As a result of SAP S/4HANA's integration with chatbot platforms, users are able to communicate with the system using natural language and receive quick responses and support.
- Intelligent Assistants: Assistants that are powered by artificial intelligence and embedded within SAP S/4HANA offer personalized recommendations, guidance that is sensitive to context, and automated support, all of which contribute to an improved user experience and productivity.

Intelligent Process Automation:

- AI for Invoice Processing: AI is utilized by SAP S/4HANA to automate the processes of verifying, matching, and approving invoices. This results in a reduction in the amount of manual labor required, an improvement in accuracy, and an acceleration of invoice processing cycles.
- AI-Driven Cash Management: With the help of intelligent algorithms, working capital management and cash visibility can be improved. These algorithms evaluate patterns of cash flow, estimate cash requirements, and optimize cash management operations.

In order to provide a concise summary of all that has been discussed so far, I would like to bring to your attention the fact that the incorporation of artificial intelligence capabilities into SAP S/4HANA opens up a substantial number of options for businesses to embark on a journey of intelligent enterprise transformation. Businesses have the ability to improve their decision-making processes, increase their operational efficiency, and provide superior customer experiences by utilizing automation that is enabled by artificial intelligence (AI), predictive analytics, intelligent insights, and enhanced user experiences. As artificial intelligence (AI) continues to advance, the partnership between AI and SAP S/4HANA has the potential to redefine business operations. This will enable enterprises to survive in a world that is becoming increasingly intelligent and data-driven.

This is meant to serve as an overview of the subject in general. For the purpose of fully maximizing the potential of artificial intelligence within the framework of your organization, it is essential to speak with SAP professionals and investigate the specific AI capabilities and features that are accessible inside your SAP S/4HANA implementation.

4. CAPABILITIES

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When it comes to deploying predictive analytics on business data, the SAP Analytics Cloud is equipped with built-in capabilities for machine learning and artificial intelligence. Faster data-driven decision-making and access to profound insights are both made possible by it for the corporate community.

The following is a list of the components belonging to the SAP Analytics Cloud that are responsible for enabling predictive capabilities:

- **Machine Learning:** The learning of processes through the utilization of data in a computerized fashion.
- **Artificial Intelligence:** Artificial intelligence refers to a machine's ability to understand and mimic human perception and emotion. To achieve intelligence, it is usually necessary to use a mix of codes, multilayer algorithms, and process approaches.
- **Augmented Analytics:** Analytical systems built on continuous learning and NLPs (natural language processing) could one day outperform humans at performing certain tasks, like human cognition and behavior.

SAP Analytics Cloud – Smart Features

Furthermore, business users may take use of SAP Analytics cloud's cognitive capabilities through self-service, as they are ready to use out of the box.

The purpose of this was to increase the number of people who utilize the tool in the community of users. These are the brilliant features:

- **Search to Insight:** One need only type in a question to participate.

It is a feature in SAP Analytics Cloud that lets users build charts from input and find relationships in the data to display the information in the best way possible. To see the results, just type normal language into the search bar. An easy way to see this in action would be to look up "Company XXX Revenue by current year vs Previous year." Utilizing the built-in algorithm, a chart is generated for further evaluation and utilization within the SAP Analytics Cloud dashboards and stories.

These superusers will find this feature to be of great assistance.

- **Smart Discovery:**

This function aids in data exploration by making use of machine learning capabilities and employs a potent mix of statistical analysis and predictive analytics.

In the event that data, dimensions, and metrics are provided, this feature has the capability of constructing a comprehensive narrative. A detailed degree of analysis can be performed on the data and reports in order to help narrow down the requirements.

- **Smart Insight:**

With the help of this function, the user is able to delve more deeply into the insights and receive additional assistance in determining the criteria and important contributing variables for a pattern. In order to deliver additional content that is related to the pattern, the algorithm carries out additional drilling depending on the data and dimensions. When it comes to applying predictive analytics on company data, the smart insights identified in the panel can be further investigated for deep insights down to the lowest granularity, thanks to the addition of story learning and artificial intelligence capabilities. Among its numerous advantages is the fact that it allows the business community to have access to deep insights and to make data-driven decisions more quickly.

- **Smart Predict:** By training the model and using the data that is provided, the built-in function assists organizations in correctly predicting the consequences of their operations. Thus, businesses can focus less on the means by which they can acquire predictions and more on the

process of coming up with ideas for what could be anticipated and the amount of data years. This feature revolutionizes the time it takes for the organization to get and evaluate forecasts. It also replaces Excel's local data manipulations with machine learning-driven predictions, which are far more powerful.

5. SMART PREDICT APPLICATION IN BUILDING PREDICTIVE SCENARIOS

The predictive scenario workspace is used to configure the smart prediction of data, which is depicted in figure 3. This is a workspace that has been preset, and it is used to develop various models in order to respond to business inquiries. In order to respond to these questions, we need to make predictions using the historical dataset, as well as use numerical data and the factors that affect it.

Fig. 3 SAP SAC Predictive scenario workspace

Let's have a look at the requirements that must be met in order to launch a predictive model. In order to construct and implement the procedure, there are three stages that can be completed.

- Source data for building the predictive model– The dataset that is provided as input is the fundamental component of the entire process of predictive analytics and the result that it produces. The actual results from the historical data are used to train the predictive model, which is then used to make predictions. The capabilities of artificial intelligence and machine learning allow for the identification of patterns and influences within the historical data that led to the known conclusion.
- The data that will be used to apply the learnings from the predictive model in order to make predictions about the probability is referred to as the target data.
- Target outcome- The machine learning algorithm that was applied to the target data produced this result. The findings are probabilities that have been forecasted and can be saved in a file or on the SAP database (HANA) according to your preference. In the process of making decisions based on data, the input, also known as source data, is of the utmost importance for businesses. The probability will be as high as the input.

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Fig. 4 SAP SAC Predictive modeling process.

SAP Predictive Analytics

This technology, known as SAP Predictive Analytics, gives you the ability to gather data and then construct predictive models based on that data, which can then be used to forecast the path that subsequent events will take. The initial stage in creating predictive models is to look for connections and patterns in both past and current data. Tools such as Automated Analytics and Expert Analytics can be used to build forecast models. Automated Analytics allows users to create simple models like classification, regression, clustering, and time series models. Expert Analytics, on the other hand, allows users to run complex analysis algorithms using the statistical analysis language and open source code in the R language. One distinctive feature of this business solution is its capacity to combine SAP Predictive Analytics with productive databases. These databases house operational data.

The creation of actual data forecasts is simplified as a result of this. You can work with straightforward prediction models without having to seek the assistance of specialists if the interface is designed to be user-friendly. The decision-making process is significantly sped up as a result. In the past, just a small percentage of illegal shipments could be found because the control was based solely on the inspector's suspicions. Nevertheless, a resolution to the issue of fraud detection was devised by the European Specialized Commission for the Control of the Transport of Animal and Animal Products. After utilizing SAP Predictive Analytics, which enabled the examination of 30% of containers, 85% of violations were identified and shown in figure 4.

Functionality

Data loaded from productive databases can be handled by SAP Predictive Analytics. SAP HANA, for example, offers support for tables and numerous views, as well as a SQL view on SAP HANA and Smart Data Access with virtual tables. In addition, you can access and manipulate data that has been imported from flat files like text files or Excel spreadsheets.

The work with data sources is simplified as a result of all of this, and the work undertaken by SAP Predictive Analytics becomes more ubiquitous as shown in figure 5.

MEASURES	Sum	fixed_acidity	volatile_acidity	citric_acid	residual_sugar	chlorides	free_sulfur_dioxide
alcohol	Sum	123	123	123	123	123	123
chlorides	Sum	10.40	0.61	0.49	2.10	0.20	
citric_acid	Sum	10.50	0.59	0.49	2.10	0.07	
density	Sum	9.90	0.50	0.24	2.30	0.10	
fixed_acidity	Sum	5.00	0.42	0.24	2.00	0.06	
free_sulfur_dioxide	Sum	8.20	0.92	0.27	2.10	0.09	
pH	Sum	10.10	0.94	0.22	3.40	0.11	
Price	Sum	8.30	0.85	0.01	2.20	0.07	
residual_sugar	Sum	7.10	0.84	0.02	4.40	0.10	
sulphates	Sum	7.40	1.19	0.00	4.25	0.10	
		7.50	0.38	0.48	2.60	0.07	
123 alcohol		9.10	0.77	0.04	1.60	0.08	
123 chlorides		7.50	1.12	0.10	3.10	0.09	
123 citric_acid		6.90	0.39	0.24	2.10	0.10	
123 density		7.30	0.57	0.09	2.30	0.07	
123 fixed_acidity		7.50	0.69	0.07	2.50	0.06	
123 free_sulfur_dioxide		10.40	0.44	0.42	1.50	0.15	
123 pH		11.60	0.47	0.44	1.60	0.15	
123 Price		7.30	0.35	0.24	2.00	0.07	
A80 Producer		7.10	0.47	0.00	2.20	0.07	
123 residual_sugar		8.30	1.02	0.02	3.40	0.08	
		8.40	0.67	0.19	2.20	0.09	

Figure 5. Getting SAP Predictive Analytics data ready

During the data model preparation stage, you can change the data source's appearance with the use of user-friendly tools with an intuitive interface. With these features, users can construct new analytical objects, such as entities, time-stamped populations, key performance indicators, and analytical records, and hide or rename existing measures and analysts. For this, there exist tools that are both easy to use and have a simple UI. Utilizing tools like Automated Analytics and Expert Analyst allows for the construction of predictive data models. Automated Analytics is a tool for data analysis and forecasting that makes use of a number of modules, such as:

1. Analytical data can be better prepared with the help of the Data Manager module. Gathering events into a series of transitions, doing preliminary analysis, and estimating text variables are all steps in sequence analysis, which is something that may be done. Aggregating the event log further allows for the unification of data from multiple sources.
2. Time series analysis, clustering, regression, classification, and a host of other analytical data models are all within the Modeler module's purview. The phenomenon can be identified, understood, and its short- and long-term evolution predicted using a time series. The Modeler also allows you to load previously created data models and develop association rules based on master data tables and transaction tables.
3. Another effective technique for evaluating data from social networks is automated analytics, which can be used to analyze data. In the Social module, you can find opportunities to mine social network data and other sorts of implicit structural relational information. Throughout the module, you will have access to these chances. Downloading a model that is already prepared to analyze data acquired from social networks is an added bonus to the ability to examine geolocations and frequent paths within these networks.
4. Using data retrieved from social media platforms, the Recommendation module allows you to build a system that suggests products to customers. Additionally, you are able to get a ready-made mechanism for making recommendations.

By analyzing the social networks of American pharmacy clients, patients and doctors were able to uncover instances of fraud. A plan including patients, doctors, and pharmacists was

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developed, and communication networks were set up, all based on previously documented instances of fraud. Consequently, fraud detection has become much more effective. The biggest Japanese restaurant chain, SKYLARK, increased the level of personalized marketing offerings to consumers by analyzing social networks and orders. Because of this, the business has devised a system that lets customers choose the best deals at the best times for them. For more precise data prediction and in-depth analysis, use the Expert Analytics tool. Time series forecasting, anomaly detection, trend analysis, classification, segment, and affinity analysis are all within reach. A variety of prediction algorithms built into Expert Analytics using the free and open-source statistical analysis language R and RAM data gathering tools allow for efficient processing of massive data sets, guaranteeing the versatility of Special Expert Analytics shown in figure 6.

Figure 6. Using Expert Analytics to construct a data prediction model

Dot matrix, parallel coordinate, cluster, and decision tree diagrams are just a few of the data visualization formats available in Expert Analytics for easy presentation of study results shown in figure 7.

Figure 7. Visualization of data

CONCLUSION

In 2023, using SAP HANA Cloud to provide Intelligent Data Applications with Machine Learning remains one of the most popular and ongoing technical methods. The reduction of data transfer, the improvement of governance, and the implementation of a uniform programming interface are all beneficial to data scientists and application builders. The machine learning capabilities of SAP HANA Cloud have the potential to play a significant part in use cases such as forecasting future demand and performing preventative maintenance on manufacturing equipment. The integration of applications with the right actionable intelligence is a game-changer for all business processes. The intense rivalry among companies to become the best in their respective industries has created a window of opportunity for niche technologies like AI and ML to revolutionize sales, finance, HR, marketing, and other related sectors. Despite the high level of competition in this industry right now, SAP Analytics Cloud has managed to solidify its position as a frontrunner. It has the ability and features to run augmented analytics and multi-scenario predictive models. Its cutting-edge features, which are available out of the box, as well as extensions that allow for the development of bespoke applications, can assist organizations in becoming successful in the future.

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